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Analysis of Beef Cattle Breeder's Food Consumption and Household Welfare During the COVID-19 Pandemic In Probolinggo Regency

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Abstract

Consumption is the value households spend purchasing different necessities (food and non-food) over a specified period. Providing enough food for families is a problem facing Indonesia, especially Regency, his Probolinggo livestock breeder's. Food consumption levels and the welfare of beef cattle breeder's change separately during the Covid-19 pandemic. This study analysed food consumption expenditure and household welfare of cattle ranchers in Regency Probolinggo. The province of Probolinggo was chosen as the site with precision. Sampling h refers to a simple sampling in which the drawn sample has been identified as being of interest with specific characteristics. The model for this survey was 88 respondents with particular criteria. The data collected is primary and secondary. Preliminary data were obtained from questionnaires and secondary data from relevant institutions such as her BPS. This study employed a descriptive quantitative research method using the consumption formula, and welfare was measured using the Breeder-Rucker Exchange Rate (NTP-T). The results of this study show that the proportion of agricultural household food consumption expenditure (PKP) is IDR 997,000 or 6.5%, breeder households' balance of non-food consumption expenditure (PKNP) is IDR 14,691,457 or 93.5%. The breeder's welfare level, calculated by the NTP-T (Breeder-French Breeder's Exchange Rate), is 105, which means that the breeder is experiencing a surplus. Breeder's income exceeds their expenditure. Therefore, it is considered that the living standard of the breeder's households in the Probolinggo District is affluent.

Keywords: Household Consumption, Welfare, Beef Cattle Breeder's

INTRODUCTION

The diet includes essential functions to meet individual and household needs. The provision of quantitative and qualitative household food is an example of household eating habits. Household consumption patterns are a comparison point in measuring indicators of public welfare such as health status, nutritional status, and poverty status. The high proportion of expenditure on food consumption in total household expenditure can be used as an indicator of poverty (Nicholas, 2001).

Income changes, general nutritional awareness, and lifestyle influence people's eating habits. Changes in consumption habits require changes in supply volumes and sales strategies so that food prices can be reasonably priced. During the Covid-19 pandemic, people's consumption habits will change directly or indirectly. Food and non-food constantly develop according to the demands of the times. The economic growth rate in any country that needs to be balanced with economic equality leads to economic inequality between families. High-income breeders consume food excessively, while poor breeders need help to meet their basic needs. One of the agricultural subsectors to be developed that has the potential to generate capital expenditures and large incomes for the actors is animal husbandry.

Human breeders and the growth of livestock are inextricably linked. According to the Director General of Animal Husbandry (1998), the people's economy has provided Indonesia with the best current and potential future chance for ruminant livestock growth (small commercial scale). According to statistics, small breeder's produce 99 per cent of domestic beef cattle.

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Various provinces in Indonesia raise beef cattle. The East Java province is big enough to raise cattle for meat. Like beef cattle producers in Indonesia, East Java has seen annual growth in the number of livestock. Between 2014 and 2019, there were 4,705,067 beef cattle in East Java, an increase of 3,949,097 heads. Probolinggo Regency's population grew from 239,564 people in 2013 to 275,764 people in 2019. East Java BPS, (2020) In Probolinggo Regency, beef cattle breeders' economics is a unique phenomenon.

Indonesia struggles with providing enough food for its citizens, particularly beef cattle ranchers in Probolinggo Regency. The amount of food consumed and the well-being of beef cattle breeders will fluctuate separately during the Covid-19 epidemic. Most of Indonesia's areas have been impacted by the Covid-19 Pandemic, including Probolinggo Regency. This issue alters food consumption habits and income levels, which has an impact on well-being levels. The COVID-19 pandemic has resulted in social restriction policies that have significantly impacted the marketing of livestock products (Sikone et al., 2022). Therefore, during the COVID-19 pandemic, preparation is required to ensure the stability of the food supply.

The author's interest in studying beef cattle producers' welfare and consumption levels during the COVID-19 epidemic stems from this phenomenon. The study "Analysis of Food Consumption and Welfare of Beef Cattle breeder's During the Covid-19 Pandemic in Probolinggo Regency" was based on this explanation.

RESEARCH METHODS

Research Location and Time

The research area was explicitly taken, namely in Probolinggo Regency. Based on the 2015 BPS Census findings, Probolinggo Regency was selected because, after Sumenep and Tuban, it is the third-rank cattle depot. Livestock in Probolinggo Regency is increasing every year. Based on BPS data in 2019, there were 275,764 beef cattle.

Data Analysis Methods

The theories put out in this study are tested and proven using descriptive quantitative research methodologies. Breeders of beef cattle in 24 areas of the Probolinggo district made up the study's population. By using simple random sampling, the sample is drawn from a population that has been chosen because it exhibits certain qualities as a study topic. Beef cattle breeder families with a total of between 3 and 5 heads and many between 6 and 10 chairs were the features of the samples used in this research. The population is randomly chosen by specified criteria using the sample selection technique, ensuring that persons with similar characteristics have an equal chance of responding. Twenty-five respondents from breeder's homes with 6 to 10 livestock and 63 respondents from breeder's households with 3 to 5 livestock each participated in this study. There were 88 responders in all.

Using the following formula (Ilham and Sinaga, 2008), the percentage of food consumption (PKP) compares food expenditure to total consumer expenditure (food + non-food):

$$PKP = \frac{PP}{PP+PNP} \times 100 \%$$

Information:

PKP = The proportion of Food Consumption

PP = Food Expenditure

PNP = Non-Food Expenditures

According to Ilham and Sinaga (2008), determining the percentage of non-food consumption involves comparing non-food spending to total consumption (food + non-food).

$$PKNP = \frac{PNP}{PP+PNP} \times 100 \%$$

Keterangan:

PKNP = The proportion of Non-Food Consumption

PP = Food Expenditure

PNP = Non-Food Expenditures

The Breeder-Livestock Exchange Rate was used to analyze the breeders' degree of welfare in this research. The NTP-T, also known as the Subsistence Term of Trade, is one of the many types of breeder Exchange Rates, including the Barter Term of Trade, Factorial Term of Trade, Income Term of Trade, and Breeder-Livestock Exchange Rate (NTP-T). It measures the relative level of welfare of the livestock community. The ratio of breeders' total household income to their whole household costs during a specific period is the definition of the Breeder-Livestock Exchange Rate (NTP-T). The NTPT calculating formula is as follows:

$$NTPT = Y_t / E_t$$

$$Y_t = Y_{Ft} + Y_{NFt}$$

$$E_t = E_{Ft} + E_{Kt}$$

this implies:

- Y_{ft} : Total income of breeders from livestock business period t
- Y_{NFt} : Total income of breeder from non-livestock business period t
- E_{ft} : Total expenditure of breeders for livestock business period t
- E_{kt} : The total expenditure of the breeder for the consumption of the family livestock period t
- t : Time period

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Conditions for Livestock Beef Cattle in the Probolinggo Regency

Probolinggo Regency is located at coordinates 1120 50`-1130 13' East Longitude and 70 40'-80 10' South Latitude with an area of ± 1,696.16 Km². Probolinggo Regency has considerable potential for livestock resources in each district. Probolinggo Regency is one of the significant livestock centres in East Java. The types of livestock cultivated by the people of Probolinggo Regency are varied, including oversized, undersized, and poultry.

The areas that make up Probolinggo Regency are home to a diverse cattle population. The table below illustrates this:

Table 1. Shows the total number of beef cattle in the Probolinggo Regency

District	Number of Beef Cattle		Total
	Male	Famale	
Sukapura	4.182	6.024	10.206
Sumber	1.778	1.850	3.628
Kuripan	3.808	5.711	9.519
Bantaran	9.429	13.487	22.916
Leces	2.869	4.585	7.454
Tegalsiwalan	3.088	4.761	7.849
Banyuanyar	5.211	6.997	12.208
Tiris	12.831	12.976	25.807
Krucil	8.288	11.525	19.813
Gading	1.502	5.530	7.032
Pakuran	2.191	11.122	13.313
Kotaanyar	4.036	10.521	14.557
Paiton	11.938	18.348	30.286
Besuk	3.242	8.044	11.286
Kraksaan	1.189	2.216	3.405
Krejengan	2.655	4.009	6.664
Pajarakan	1.082	1.028	2.110
Maron	4.915	5.628	10.543
Gending	767	2.548	3.315
Dringu	5.851	716	6.567
Wonomerto	2.382	4.566	6.948
Lumbang	5.304	6.911	12.215
Tongas	3.621	9.087	12.708
Sumberasih	7.188	4.066	11.254
Total	109.347	162.256	271.603

Source: Probolinggo Regency In Numbers, 2020

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The table shows that the largest slaughter cattle population is in Paiton District, with a population of 30,286 heads, and the smallest is in Pajarakan District, with a population of 2,110 leaders. However, the beef cattle population is distributed almost evenly among the districts of Probolinggo Regency.

Characteristics of Respondents

The findings indicated that most respondents had family groups with an average of 4-6 members. The family patriarch, their wife, and their kids make up the typical family unit. Family size significantly impacts food demands; the more significant the household, the higher the market.

Table 2. Number of Family Members

No	Number of Household Members	Total	Percentage (%)
1	1-3	24	27
2	4-6	59	67
3	7-9	5	6
Total		88	100

Source: Processed research data in 2020.

According to Table 23, respondents who have family dependents between 4-6 people make up the most significant percentage of respondents (67%), followed by respondents who have family dependents between 1-3 people (27%), and respondents who have family dependents between 7-9 people (6%).

The responder in this research, the family head, varied in age from 22 to 60. The following table shows the distribution of samples by age group:

Table 3. Age of the Head of the family

No	Age	Total	Percentage (%)
1	20-39	6	7
2	40-59	65	76
3	60-79	17	19
Total		88	100

Source: Processed research data in 2020.

Based on the table, it can be seen that out of 100 respondents, the majority are in the age group of 40 to 59, namely 65 people (76%), followed by the age group of 60 to 79, as many as 17 people (19%). 20-39, that is, as many as six people (7%).

Between elementary school and high school graduation, the respondent sample of beef cattle ranchers had formal schooling. Following is a breakdown of respondents by educational attainment:

Table 4. Educational Level of the Family Head

No	Education	Total	Percentage (%)
1	elementary school	43	48
2	Junior high school	30	34
3	Senior high school	15	18
Total		88	100

Source: Processed research data in 2020.

Based on the table, It is evident that out of 100 respondents, the majority have an elementary school education, and as many as 43 people (48%). There are 30 people with junior high school education (34%), and then 15 people have a high school diploma (18%).

Between 3 and 10 heads of livestock are kept by respondents who are beef cattle producers. The number of respondents' livestock was as follows:

Table 5. Rate of Livestock Ownership

No	Livestock Ownership	Total	Percentage (%)
1	3-4	46	52
2	5-6	25	28
3	7-8	13	14
4	9-10	4	6
Total		88	100

Source: Processed research data in 2020.

Based on the table informing the number of owners of Beef Cattle cattle respondents, 46 people (52%) had 3-4 heads, 25 respondents had 5-6 heads of livestock, 13 respondents had 7-8 livestock next, which had 9-10 heads as many as four people (6%).

Food Consumption

The needs of beef cattle breeder include food and non-food requirements. Peasant families are financed with money to satisfy their necessities. Total household consumption is the cost incurred to finance the consumption of all household members. Food consumption is the number of foods and drinks a person eats/drinks to meet their physical needs. Agricultural household consumption includes two consumptions, namely food consumption and non-food consumption. In this study, there were several expenditures for food, namely raw food ingredients such as rice, meat, vegetables, and fruits. Items already prepared, such as snacks, bread, tea, coffee, and milk, and semifinished goods like sugar, noodles, eggs, and oil. The price is determined each month. The table below shows the monthly expenditure on food.

The consumption composition may be utilized in the breeder's family to determine the degree of the local economy's well-being. The lower the percentage of food consumption to total consumption, the better the financial status of the neighbourhood (BPS, 2006). Based on this, with the Covid-19 pandemic, there will be a global economic recession, so there will be a decrease in people's purchasing power, including in Probolinggo Regency. The following is a table of the total household food consumption of the breeder.

Table 6. The total amount of food that breeder households in Probolinggo Regency consume.

No	Description	Total consumption (IDR)
1	Minimum	512.800
2	Maximum	2.380.000
	Average	997.000

Source: Processed research data in 2020.

By table 6, The amount of food consumed by breeder households is a minimum of IDR 512,800, the maximum food consumption is IDR 2,380,000, and the average food consumption for the most prominent Breeder households is IDR 997,000

Non-Food Consumption

Costs associated with non-food consumption include taxes, insurance, housing, clothes, and health care. Breeder families in Probolinggo Regency consumed the following amounts of non-food during the COVID-19 period:

Table 7. Consumption of all non-food items by breeder households in the Probolinggo Regency

No	Description	Non-Food Consumption (IDR)
1	Minimum	6.435.800
2	Maximum	31.450.000
	Average	14.691.457

Source: Processed research data in 2020.

The non-food consumption of breeder households is a minimum of IDR 6,435,800 and a maximum of IDR 31,450,000, with an average total of IDR 14,691,457 for the 88 respondents.

The ratio of expenditure on food consumption to the total spending of breeder households

The ratio of food expenditures is the amount of food expenditure to the total cost. The level of consumer spending depends on the life cycle of a person. A person's consumption cycle begins when the person is no longer working, so his parents or debts help them finance consumption expenditures. If a person is already working, they set aside part of their income to pay off debts or retire.

The income level affects the level of consumer expenditure for food and non-food consumption—the level of consumer spending about income using ratios. The share of food expenditure is the percentage of food to total spending. Next comes the proportion of breeder households.

Table 8. The proportion of household final consumption expenditure.

Description	Nominal (IDR)	Proportion (%)
Food Consumption	997.000	6,5
Non-Food Consumption	14.691.457	93,5
Total Consumption	15.688.457	100

Source: Processed field data as of 2020

Total expenditure is food consumption plus non-food consumption. The total consumption expenditure in this study is IDR 15,688,457. Based on the table above, the amount of food expenditure is IDR 997,000, and non-food expenses are IDR 14.691.457 of the total consumption.

Based on the above information, food expenditure is lower than non-food expenditure. The share of consumer spending on food in total spending is 6.5%, and the percentage of consumer spending on non-food in consumer spending is 93.5%. The portion of food expenditure is tiny because the breeder always uses the income from selling livestock to buy seeds.

Breeder households that can afford to meet their food and non-nutritional needs. According to Engel's law, the share of food expenditure in total expenditure decreases as income increases. With increasing incomes, households can buy food of the best nutritional quality, where food is not only about satisfying hunger but also about meeting the family's dietary needs.

Welfare Level

The level of welfare is essential to maintaining social and economic stability and advancing education. An important indicator of breeders' interest is the income level and its balance with expenses. The measuring instrument commonly used is the Breeder Exchange Rate (NTP). The Breeder exchange rate is an example of the Breeder's purchasing power/purchasing power to products purchased/paid for by the Breeder, including purchased consumption and production inputs. The higher the breeder's Breeder's exchange rate, the better the breeder's Breeder's purchasing power towards consumer goods and means of production. The following are the results of the Breeder's Exchange Rate (NTP) in Breeder households in Probolinggo Regency.

Table 9. Breeders' degree of financial security in their homes

No	Description	Value
1	Minimum	43
2	Maximum	196
Average		105

Source: Processed field data as of 2020

Based on the table shows that the minimum Breeder Exchange Rate (NTP) for beef cattle breeders in Probolinggo Regency is 43, meaning that the level of breeders' welfare is still shallow. According to calculations, when the breeder's exchange rate is below 100 (NTP<100), Breeder experience a deficit with a minor increase in production prices compared to the rise in consumer prices and production costs.

The maximum breeder exchange rate of 196 indicates high well-being for breeder families. Breeders have a surplus if the breeder exchange rate is determined to be more than 100 (NTP>100). The cost of manufacturing increased higher than consumer prices and production expenses combined. Due to its great worth, it falls under the category of being very affluent.

The average exchange rate of Breeder households in Probolinggo Regency is 105, meaning that producers are surplus, and their income is more significant than their expenses. Therefore, the social level of Breeder households in Probolinggo Regency is relatively affluent.

CONCLUSION

Based on the description of the results of the study and its discussion, the following conclusions can be drawn:

- 1) The percentage of breeder families' non-food consumption spending (PKNP) is IDR 14,691,457, or 93.5%, while the proportion of their food consumption expenditure (PKP) is IDR 997,000, or 6.5%.
- 2) The level of household welfare of beef cattle breeders is based on the calculation of NTP-T (Breeder's Exchange Rate) of 105, meaning that the breeder has a surplus, and the Breeder's income is higher than the level of expenditure. Thus the status of household welfare of breeders in Probolinggo Regency includes prosperity.

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